

**DEBT MANAGEMENT OFFICE
NIGERIA**

**DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL
TERRITORY AS AT SEPTEMBER 30, 2020
AMOUNT IN NAIRA**

SN	STATE	DEBT STOCK (N)
1	ABIA	89,625,183,223.63
2	ADAMAWA	116,893,015,728.22
3	AKWA IBOM	239,209,746,919.94
4	ANAMBRA	59,013,845,976.50
5	BAUCHI	96,295,156,054.65
6	BAYELSA	147,890,364,425.52
7	BENUE	128,504,831,985.51
8	BORNO	90,369,619,974.97
9	CROSS-RIVER	164,100,248,065.57
10	DELTA	235,860,479,518.82
11	EBONYI	41,273,963,348.58
12	EDO	78,121,931,567.35
13	EKITI	77,072,844,596.55
14	ENUGU	62,436,497,337.43
15	GOMBE	90,503,282,526.59
16	IMO	158,174,623,598.44
17	JIGAWA	36,039,966,666.27
18	KADUNA	72,503,331,825.58
19	KANO	116,999,956,070.87
20	KATSINA	44,416,331,545.82
21	KEBBI	67,315,419,254.61
22	KOGI	73,314,904,696.35
23	KWARA	63,366,236,320.99
24	LAGOS	493,318,231,673.72
25	NASARAWA	61,299,995,407.54
26	NIGER	65,601,207,473.58
27	OGUN	150,085,294,306.87
28	ONDO	72,207,072,705.52
29	OSUN	134,898,800,101.79
30	OYO	99,943,412,785.14
31	PLATEAU	127,012,622,276.11
32	RIVERS*	266,936,225,793.65
33	SOKOTO	48,089,793,082.99
34	TARABA	122,746,246,998.60
35	YOBE	29,230,547,154.25
36	ZAMFARA	79,286,884,618.37
37	FCT	90,225,199,641.10
Total		4,190,183,315,247.99

Important Notes

- 1 Domestic Debt Stock for Five (5) States: Bauchi, Bayelsa, Ogun, Ondo, Osun and the FCT as at September 30, 2020.
- 2 Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty One (31) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe and Zamfara as at June 30, 2020.
- 3 Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018